

PAPER A: CASE STUDY

Factors Influencing the Spread of *Plasmodia Falciparum*. Case Study Daura Local Government, Katsina State

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Abstract

The death rate from *Plasmodia falciparum* in Daura Local Government (DLG) Area of Nigeria is very alarming and has affected people of all ages. The majority of illness cases treated in hospitals are caused by *P. falciparum*. *Plasmodia falciparum* is found to be responsible for a high mortality rate when the total mortality rate from a particular health facility in Daura Local Government is summed together. Others are linked to different parasites or microorganisms, including bacteria and viruses. This revelation instigates the allocation of more attention to how this parasite breeds and how they become endemic. Furthermore, how factors like poor healthcare infrastructure, zero drug distribution, parasite resistance to drugs, poorly constructed rural dwelling as a result of poverty, non-cooperation with program facilitators because of the high level of illiteracy, lack of strategic control methods, drug resistance, noncompliance to drug dosage, dearth of quality control of drugs, dearth of effective rural drug distribution mechanism, widespread of presumptive treatment and incorrect diagnosis/inadequate diagnostic equipment can be addressed to bring the mortality rate to a very minimal rate are discussed extensively. If those challenges are tackled, *Plasmodia falciparum* will be eradicated in no time from Daura Local Government as well as the entire country.

External Link:**Keywords:** Daura, Plasmodia falciparum, Healthcare, Malaria, Mosquito, DiseaseURL: www.dfajournals.com/jpms

1.0. | Introduction

Daura Local Government is a town in Katsina State in North-Western Nigeria. It is the spiritual home of the Hausa people, having coordinates (1302111N80191411E) as obtained in

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(Wikipedia, 2022). It is no news that *Plasmodia falciparum* is highly endemic in Daura Local Government area of Katsina State in Nigeria. It is a malaria-causing parasite that brings about a high motility rate among rural dwellers and the community at large, affecting people of all ages. Between 2018-2022 out of 70% of patients who visits health care facilities across the country with the case malaria, 40%, and 11% resulted in childhood and maternal deaths respectively. In Nigeria, the financial loss due to malaria annually is estimated to be about 132 billion naira in form of treatment cost, prevention, and loss of man-hours (UM, 2012).

Malaria has a worldwide distribution, affecting people of all ages, with an enormous burden amounting to 300-500 million clinical cases per year. Globally, 10 new cases of malaria occur every second, which is a major public health problem in the tropics where about 40% of the world's population lives. It is responsible for more than a million deaths each year, where 90% occur in sub-Saharan Africa. Malaria is caused by four different protozoa in the plasmodium genus; namely, *Plasmodium vivax* (is more prevalent in low endemic areas), *P. oval*, *P. malaria*, and *P. falciparum* (most dangerous of the four). The *P. falciparum* has a life cycle in the mosquito vector as well as in the human host. The *Anopheles gambiae* mosquito is the vector responsible for the transmission of malaria. The prevalence of malaria is dependent on the abundance of the female anopheles species, the propensity of the mosquito to bite, the rate at which it bites, its longevity, and the rate of development of the plasmodium parasite inside the mosquito. When the female mosquito bites and sucks the blood of a person infected with the malaria parasite she becomes infected. She then transmits the parasites to the next human host she bites. Malaria incubates in the human host for about 8-10 days. The spread of malaria needs conditions favorable to the survival of the mosquito and the plasmodium parasite. Temperatures of approximately 70-90°F and relative humidity of at least 60% are most conducive for the mosquito (Isegbe Onah et al., 2017). The prevalence of malaria cases in Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa is at an alarming rate. The success of its malaria control programs will have a significant impact on overall control.

Most malaria deaths occur at home without confirmation of the diagnosis. The reality is that in the poorest, rural areas, where malaria takes its highest toll, it is difficult to obtain accurate data and derive meaningful malaria statistics. During their illness, many patients struggle, often unsuccessfully to access basic health care (Isegbe Onah et al., 2017). For those that succeed, the care may be of dubious quality and ineffective (Kitua, 2004). In response to this terrible situation, the global community is now taking steps to deliver more effective intervention throughout Africa,

including drug combinations with an artemisinin derivative and anti-vector measures (Nnamonu et al., 2020). The dramatic success of these measures in a few specific areas, such as KwaZulu in South Africa (Oladokun et al., 2012), and the Tanzanian Island of Zanzibar (Uneke, 2011), has inspired a new call for global eradication (Chukwuocha, 2011). Achieving this ambitious goal depends on the development of new tools to treat, prevent and monitor malaria (Ukpe et al., 2013)(Moonasar et al., 2013).

Dauda et al. (2011) in their work, made mention that health authorities in Nigeria have for many years promoted national malaria control measures such as the use of insecticide-treated bed nets (ITNs), indoor residual spray of insecticides (IRS), intermittent preventive treatment (IPT) for pregnant women and children and the use of artemisinin combined therapy (ACT) as first line of treatment to reduce the prevalence of the disease in the country. The researcher mostly limits his study to pregnant women in DLG which is believed not to be enough because the community does not comprise of pregnant women only. The author did not state measures that could be employed to the reduction of malaria. Elsewhere, Prevalence et al. (2017) obtained data on various infectious diseases using cluster analysis in DLG and other two zones in Katsina state, where it was found that malaria is more prevalent in the area compared to other zones followed by cholera and typhoid fever. The same author mentioned many infectious diseases without given special attention to malaria which is the most prevalent disease in the location. Despite the effort put by some bodies (Nigerian National Malaria Control Policy, United Nations (UN), and the World Bank etc.) into the eradication of this parasite (*Plasmodia falciparum*) more measures need to be employed in other to mitigate or eradicate the problem. This paper pinpoints the prominent factors that lead to the high spread of this parasite in the Daura Local Government and the possible solutions we need to employ in other to curtail the problem and reduce the havoc caused by this parasite.

2.1. | Global Malaria Burden

About 107 countries and territories involving about 3.2 billion people are still at risk of malaria attack as of 2004 (Groep et al., 2013). Present estimates suggest that around 350-500 million clinical disease episodes occur annually (Mlozi et al., 2015). Around 60% of clinical cases and over 80% of the deaths due to malaria occur in Africa, south of the Sahara (Mlozi et al., 2015). It is the second leading cause of death from infectious diseases in Africa after HIV/AIDS and is also a leading cause of mortality in under-five children accounting for 20% of death and constituting 10% of the total disease burden of the African continent (Nnamonu et al., 2020). Malaria kills a child somewhere in the world every 30 seconds.

Over 90% of the malaria burden occurs in Sub-Saharan Africa (N et al., 2016)(Musoke et al., 2015). In endemic areas, malaria infection in pregnancy is believed to account for up to a quarter of all cases of severe maternal anemia and for 10- 20% of low birth-weight babies (Moonasar et al., 2013). Each year, more than 500,000 women die during pregnancy or childbirth (Mbbs, 2016) and more than four million babies die in the first 28 days of life, accounting for 38% of mortality in children of five years old or under, worldwide (Kweka et al., 2013). Maternal malaria infection is estimated to account for 3-8% of all infant deaths (BRUCE-CHWATT, 1951). Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Sudan, and Uganda account for nearly 50% of global malaria deaths (Brieger et al., 2001). High rates of maternal and prenatal mortality have been observed in the different regions of Sudan. Malaria and anemia were the major causes of these high levels of mortality (Blumberg & Frean, 2007).

2.2. | Spread of *Plasmodium falciparum*

Despite the effort of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and the government itself in the eradication of this parasite, many setbacks tend to make measures taken ineffective.

2.2.1. | Drug Resistance

Parasite resistance to artemisinin which is an important component in the treatment of this parasite (*Plasmodia falciparum*) has been confirmed in many wards in the local government. In Nigeria, antimalarial drug resistance is recognized as one of the causes of treatment failures. Chloroquine (CQ) and sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) have become resistant to the parasite and are therefore no longer considered first-line therapeutic agents. Those of the ACTs have not been confirmed. Unless foreign bodies and the Nigerian government looked critically into ways to solve this problem, the growing power of this parasite won't stop (Kitua, 2004).

2.2.2. | High Level of Illiteracy

A study in Daura Local Government shows that residents of both urban and rural areas still have misconceptions regarding the cause of malaria. Some attributed malaria to an act of the Divine while others attributed it to spirits/charm, poor nutrition, and stress (Joseph et al., 2017). These are major socio-cultural setbacks in malaria treatment and control. All these contribute to the discrepancies in health-seeking behavior and may cause a delay in seeking appropriate treatment.

2.2.3. | Dearth of Quality Control of Drugs

Due to the high level of lawlessness in Nigeria and noncompliance with government bodies regulating drug use in the country, the use of adulterated drugs across the country has become a normal day-to-day business, especially with people selling fake drugs for personal gain. Since nearly all malaria treatment occurs at home, and this practice is common to the people of Daura, the people rely mainly on drugs sold over the counter (Isegbe Onah et al., 2017).

2.2.4. | Inadequate Malaria Epidemiological Data

Epidemiological data concerning malaria morbidity and mortality in Nigeria is inadequate (Ikpeze & Ugbor, 2015). Most studies were confined to pregnant mothers and children under the age of five and mostly hospital-based records. Again, much is not known about malaria mortality and morbidity in Daura local government.

2.2.5. | Dearth of Effective Rural Drug Distribution Mechanism

In Daura Local Government It is very obvious that people have bad health care systems. Usually, there are no accessible roads to the health centers, which in turn are poorly equipped and have inadequate drugs for malaria treatment (Hemingway et al., 2002).

2.2.6. | Incorrect Diagnosis/Inadequate Diagnostic Equipment

High-quality parasite-based diagnosis has remained unavailable to most patients in Daura Local Government (Groepe et al., 2013). Maintenance of quality and effective microscopy services, requires an organized health system infrastructure, including the provision of high-quality supplies and reagents, the presence of satisfactory microscopes, maintenance and technical competence, an adequate workplace environment, and the ability to prepare usable blood films (Erhun WO et al., 2005). Field microscopy, where established, often falls short of these requirements (Enayati & Hemingway, 2010).

2.2.7. | Inadequate Malaria Prevention Financing in Nigeria

Because the majority of the dwellers in Daura Local Government are poor this brings about poor house structure as seen in the figures, above the level of poverty directly affects the choice of the house in which this dwells live in and also affects the choice of the environment which the dwellers live exposing these dwellers to high contact rate with infective mosquitoes, as insecticide-treated nets are unaffordable to the poorest if they must pay for them, and lack of resources prevents people from seeking timely

healthcare (Dua & Acharya, 2012). Studies have revealed that a substantially higher prevalence of malaria infection occurs among the poorest population group (Chitnis et al., 2008) and that the poorest were most susceptible to contracting malaria (Chukwuocha, 2011).

2.2.8. | *Availability and Access to Standard Health Care System and Drugs*

The people of Daura lack good roads to the health centers, poorly equipped centers, inadequate drugs for malaria treatment, and substandard antimalarial medicines, and as well as the available ratio of patients to doctors is alarmingly high. As a result of this, this is encouraging patients to seek treatment from unauthorized local service providers, which often leads to further complications. (Chatterjee, 2018).

2.2.9. | *Lack of Proper Sanitation*

The people of Daura Local Government have poor sanitation culture and agencies responsible for environmental care are not enforcing them to take good care of their environment which encourage the breeding of parasite. some of these dwellers are intentionally carrying out some domestic practices that help to breed this parasite like digging open suck way to store wastewater that come from their home as seen in the figure above (Byass et al., 2017).

2.2.10. | *Inadequate Cleaning of Drainage*

Despite the effort put in the construction of drainage if cleaning practice is not involved continuously to enhance the flow however overtime waste like polyethylene bags and leaves eventually gets back into the drainage thereby increasing the nutrient level of the water which is sweetable for breeding of this parasite. thus obstructing the flow of water leading to stagnancy and flooding which gives room for the parasite to breed this kind of drainage menace is very common in the drainages in Daura Local Government (Bugssa & Tedla, 2020).

Figure 1: Unclean Drainage located in kurrubai 1 adjacent to police headquarter Daura Local Government, Katsina State

2.2.11. | *House structure*

A survey was conducted to check the number of housing factors affecting malaria success in 2022 in Daura Local Government we could see the houses lack screening doors and windows lack of installation of plywood calling on open eaves and holes in the walls left unclosed. the effect of house structure concerning mosquito density can't be overemphasized because mosquito in our environment is very eminent which can influence the exposure of mosquito, especially in rural areas. So, there is a need to improve the housing structure in Daura Local Government.

(a) Shaiskawaw Line 3

(b) Shaiskawaw Line 5

Figure 2: House Structures at Some Locations in Daura Local Government, Katsina State

2.2.12. | *Pit Consideration*

This practice is very common in Daura Local Government, which tends to facilitate Mosquito breeding which is unhygienic, this mosquito tends to breed in a place where they could find stagnant water, whereby pit digging gives room for adequate breeding of this mosquito parasite. that is why the dewellersa must stop this practice of digging pit toilet and the one been dug in front of our houses, to collect

waste water from our houses to deal with the issue of this parasite spread in Daura Local Government.

Figure 3: Frontage Pit Located at Zango Ward, Line 5

3.0. | Conclusion

More attention needs to be given to this parasite (*Plasmodia falciparum*) to curtail the havoc it might cause to human health to bring it to a minimal or zero level like in developed countries like England. Thus, previously, measures taken were the distribution of insecticide mosquito nets across localities in the country including Daura Local Government, and the involvement of national and international bodies. Some of these bodies are Indoor Residual Spray (IRS), Nigerian National Malaria Control Policy, United Nations (UN), and the World Bank. Despite that more strategies needs to be adopted, especially funding, research, and vaccine search. Fundamentally, the funding should target vaccine findings, public enlightenment on environmental health, upgrading and creation of more bodies for its effective eradication or control, construction of better toilets other than pit latrines, proper housing structure, provision of community sanitary tools, ensuring the availability and access to Standard Health Care System and Drugs, procurements of diagnostic equipment, the subsidy of mosquito nets to rural dwellers that a financially weak, ensuring drug quality control, and the creation of nonresistance malaria drugs. The forgone strategy will make malaria a thing of the past in Daura Local Government as well as many other communities in Nigeria.

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Conflict of Interest

We declare no conflict of interest.

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Research	X	
Methodology	X	
Project Management		X
Means		X
Writing-original draft	X	

Writing-revision and editing	X	
Discussion of Result		X
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